

g__Aphanomyces

Wilcoxon, p = 0.03

Wilcoxon test -Differential analysis on center-log normalised 18S libraries, Preak Sdei

relative_abundance

g__Monhystera

Wilcoxon, p = 0.043

g__Vermamoeba

Wilcoxon, p = 0.023

group

g__Ceratiomyxella

Wilcoxon, p = 0.026

g__Pseudouroleptus

Wilcoxon, p = 0.011

g__Vermamoeba

Wilcoxon, p = 0.046

Wilcoxon test - Differential analysis on center-log normalised 18S libraries, Rovieng

group